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MAJOR DETERMINANTS OF POPULATION GROWTH

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Abstract

The term ‘ Population Growth ’ or ‘ Population change ’ is used in its broadest connotation to cover changes in Population numbers , Inhabitants of a territory during a specific period of time, Irrespective the fact, whether the changes is positive or negative (Chandna, 1992, p – 81). Though the growth signifies both an Increase and decrease, therefore, stands for changes of numbers nevertheless the choice of growth over change is mainly due to the fact that very few countries of the world have recorded a decline in their population and that too has been marginal and for short period. On the contrary, in most of the countries populations are growing so rapidly that world population growth has become one of the major problems of the present.

The most important fact about a population is the continuous process of change of its numbers. This process of change results basically from fertility and mortality behavior of a population in addition to these vital processes, the immigration on the other provides a measure of change, irrespective of its increase or decrease of number is referred to as population growth. Demographic fact about a population is its rate of growth (Boque, 1969, p-37).

Population growth can be measured both in terms of absolute numbers and percentage. The absolute growth is obtained by subtracting the population of an earlier date from that of latter date, While the percentage change is obtained by dividing the absolute change by the population of the earlier date and multiplying it with 100. Population geographers have often calculated the percent growth of population for a period of ten years. This period normally synchronizes with the inter-censal period, such a growth rate is calculated with the help of actual

population count at the earlier census and it's generally known as actual rate of population growth.

Apart from the absolute increase and the actual growth rate of population per annum, one of the most common measures is the geometrical annual rate of increase. The rate of geometric growth is one in which the population is supposed to increase or decrease at the same rate over such unit of time, Say each year. The geometric rate of increase is the type of change where the compounding takes place at a certain constant interval say a year. It is a useful rate and may be helpful in assessing the accuracy of vital and migration statistics. Various techniques have been adopted for measuring the annual growth rate of population. The results obtained vary from measure as the variable taken and methods adopted are not always the same in all the cases. However, the method adopted by the U.N. Demographic year Books have been commonly used for computing the annual growth rate of population.

Determinants of population Growth:

Population growth varies from nations to nations and among different section of a nation. These variations are caused by several factors directly or indirectly. Some of the selected determinants are demographic, economic , social , political and technological.

Demographic Determinants:

It is one of the chief determinants of population growth. It Influences through fertility, mortality and migration levels. Fertility and mortality are more important than migration. They determine the number of people for the earth as a whole. The rate of growth is primarily determined by the relation between birth and death rates. Migration also affects growth, but in respect of regional variations and open populations otherwise it is ineffective as determinant of growth of population. Fertility as an important determinant of population growth, does not concern only to women themselves but also that community to which they belonged. Fertility has a direct bearing on the growth, size and structure of a population. The growth of the population depends mainly on fertility. In population dynamics fertility is the positive force, through which the population expands, counteracting the forces of attrition caused by mortality. If this

replacement of human beings is not adequate i.e. if the number of deaths in particular society continues to be more than that of births the society would face the danger of becoming extinct. Apart from the immediate effects of fertility on the size and growth of population fertility change (upsets) the age structure of population which in turn changes / determine the proportion of population in different age groups. A high fertility includes an age structure which is highly weighted towards the younger ages.

Most of the developing countries at present have completed family size of 5-6 children. If this rate of fertility continues in coming generation, it means an infant boy and girl who will go on to have 6 children is to add these people plus their 36 children, 216 great grand children and so on. (Bhende, 1988, p-298).

Historically, the mortality had played a dominant role in determining the growth of population, the size of which fluctuated in the past mainly in response to variations in mortality. The increase in the population of European countries following the Industrial revolution in the seventeenth century was mainly due to a decline in the death rates. The developing countries, which are undergoing a typical demographic transition, have also been affected initially by the falls in the death rates. In India, too the most important factor that has contributed to a very high growth rate which kept the population during last four decades has been the sudden and phenomenal fall in death rate and before independence it was the high mortality rate which is responsible for the much feared population explosion.

Migration is the Third dynamic constituent of population growth. A population may gain in size by experiencing an influx of migration and it may diminish in size by an exodus of some of its members to join another population. Both international and internal migration has played a very important role in the history of population growth of any country (O gale, 1969, p-62).

Differences in the natural increase among the states of a country are often rather very small, while in reality there are wide variations in their growth rates. The only principal mechanism for such wide variations is internal migration (Jones, 1981, p -112). The rural to urban migration is usually associated with industrialization and urbanization. Migrants from the rural areas tend to adopt the urban way of life, which in turn has a direct impact on reducing the

fertility a striking feature of the migration is that while changes caused by the fertility and mortality in the size and structure of the population are never drastic migration may change the size, Structure and sex ratio of the population quite drastically at any point of times. Regional growth rates results from both differential natural increase and migration increase leading to growth of population.

Economic Determinants:

Economic factors stand second in their potential for effecting population growth. It might be assumed that economic hard times would cause people to migrate in search of jobs and thus increase migration.

However, since the rate of migration actually declines during difficult economic times, one could speculate that there is reluctance to leave familiar places (Kemmeys, 1988, p – 9).

The Time honoured adage that population grows in response to the demand for labour has the characteristics of an over worked half- truth it is eminently reasonable, yet presents only one side of the problems certainly the massive demands for labour by the expanding American economy in the nineteenth century did lead to emigration from the old world just as the industrial revolution in Britain created the opportunity for rural urban migration but there can be population growth without there being a demand for labour, while labour shortages can be chronic without inducing population growth (Simon, 1977, p-102).

The economic factors also influence population growth through the standard of living. The inverse relationship between improving living standards and mortality has often been observed. Particularly as it weaves through better diet, clothing and housing to ameliorate the worst excesses of those diseases which stem from under nourishment and poverty (Noods, 1982, p-169). In advanced countries the progress towards ever higher standards of living and wages was self Perpetuating and that it could be stopped only by perversion of the system, through monopoly was bad government or class struggle. (Clarke 1907, p-89). Fundamental changes in the economic development associated with the agricultural manufacturing and tertiary states of development put strains on the structure of population an aspect of population growth as it adjusts from rural to urban and from to cerebral style of life and modes of employment. In

nineteenth centuries it was fully observed that the increase of food supply regulated the growth of population. (Chalmers, 1932, p.56-57).

Social Determinants:

The social class factor is most important in accounting for differential population growth. Mortality fertility and migration patterns are all empirically related to differences in class (Woods, 1982, p-11). The pure social factor can be thought of as expressing a large variety of factors the Cultural, religious linguistic, ethnic and racial characteristics of a population growth which can all be important in giving it a distinctive demographic structure. Such attributes are often used as signs of inferiority or superiority and are thus potential means of self or imposed isolation, which can itself have a variety of demographics and spatial expressions.

The oppression involved has also established demographic distinction between minority and majority. The relative standing of woman, the form of marriage pattern the organization of family groups, whether nuclear or extended. Together with the inheritance laws are all ways in which social roles are formed and norms are established. Their roles and norms can mean the difference on the one hand, a society having monogamous marriages that are subtracted when bride and groom are in their late twenties or thirties, where nuclear families and inheritance. The fertility of females in the first mentioned society is likely to be lower than that of those in the second, although which of the contributing variables in the most important increasing the tendency domains to be seen (Woods, 1982, p-12).

Political Determinants:

The explosive growth of world's population, with its consequent demand for more food stuffs, keeps the world in a state of potential crisis. The green revolution in different parts of the world, which brought out more productive cereals like the miracle like in Philippines and Sri Lanka and wheat, in Mexico, India, Pakistan let the populationist score a point only temporarily over the promotion of the issue of great priority Japan which achieved a precipitous decline in its birth rate mainly through abortions, still remains the prime example of the east to have contained the crisis successfully (Chandna, 1979, p-335).

Ironically, the population control measures in the recent part have not been very effective in the large sized less developed countries like India, Indonesia, Pakistan where the crisis is felt most strongly. In such countries the problems are several the numbers are great, the annual increment is substantial the masses are illiterate and the majority of population continues to struggle to wrest a meager harvest from landholding with the slowly improving term technology under the circumstances the measure of greater productivity still appears to lie in more man power, and that inhibits the acceptance of the realization about the need for birth control measures is meager but also the dissemination of the required information and devices to control births is slow and difficult (Chandna, 1992, p- 304),

It is also an expression of an assortment of variables which are concerned with resulting population growth. The distinctive government policies enacted in the nation are bound to influence the size and structure of the population. The effects of political factors are not of course, limited to child bearing. Immigration and migration laws and policies can have a significant impact on the movement of people from country to country and place to place can have the effect of decreasing death rates (Kemmerer, 1988).

Technological Determinants:

The technological determinants can be thought of as comprising following aspects invention, practical development adoption and mass use which are to varying degree responses to stimulation from the other determinants. Advances in medical, transport, agricultural and industrial technologies have all contributed to rapid population growth.

Medical advances in the field of real contraception oral technology have meant that birth control can now be practiced effectively by the many millions of women who wish to space out the children's births and limit their completed family size. However these developments have not been always whole beneficial The ever widening gap between the technologically advanced western states and those in the third world means that health services are differentially distributed and there are wild slipperiest in living standards both having important implications for long term rapid population growth.

There is a need to comprehend these determinants and to work on these factors to keep a check on the increasing population. Each oth the abovementione determinant plays its role in its own

way and each need to be tackled with designing and implementing specific framework and guidelines.

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